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Implementing Anti-Corruption Education in Higher Education: Building a Corruption-Free Generation

Implementasi Pendidikan Antikorupsi di Perguruan Tinggi: Membangun Generasi Bebas Korupsi

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Abstract

The role of students in efforts to eradicate corruption is certainly not by enforcing the law, the active role of students is expected to be more focused on preventing corruption through participation in building an anti-corruption culture in society. Students as agents of change are expected to bring about change and become anti-corruption drivers in society. However, to be able to play an active role, students need to have sufficient knowledge about corruption and anti-corruption values. Anti-corruption education is here aimed at educating students to have a strong character and proper understanding in order to prevent corruption and become a young generation that is free from corrupt practices.

Keywords

Anti-corruption Education, Agent of Change, Corruption Prevention.

Abstrak

Peran mahasiswa dalam upaya pemberantasan korupsi tentu tidak dengan cara menegakan hukum, peran aktif mahasiswa diharapkan lebih fokus mencegah korupsi melalui partisipasi membangun budaya anti korupsi di masyarakat. Mahasiswa sebagai agen perubahan diharapkan dapat membawa perubahan dan menjadi penggerak antikorupsi di masyarakat. Namun untuk dapat berperan aktif, mahasiswa perlu memiliki pengetahuan yang cukup tentang korupsi dan nilai-nilai antikorupsi. Pendidikan antikorupsi hadir bertujuan untuk mendidik mahasiswa agar memiliki karakter yang kuat dan bekal pemahaman yang layak agar dapat mencegah terjadinya korupsi dan menjadai generasi muda yang bersih dari praktik korupsi.

Kata Kunci

Pendidikan Antikorupsi, Agen Perubahan, Pencegahan Korupsi.

A. Introduction

Corruption is literally understood as depravity, moral decay, dishonesty, immorality, and a deviation from integrity or ethical principles.¹ More broadly, corruption refers to wrongful conduct involving unethical practices for personal or group interests. It is typically committed by individuals holding positions of authority within public institutions who abuse the powers entrusted to them in the performance of their official duties. Such misconduct adversely affects society, causes financial losses to the state, and infringes upon the rights and interests of other citizens. Fundamentally, corruption is driven by personal or group interests, resulting in the unlawful appropriation of public resources or benefits to which the perpetrators are not entitled.

¹ Tim Penulis Buku Pendidikan Anti Korupsi, *Pendidikan Anti Korupsi untuk Perguruan Tinggi* (Jakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 2011).23

In Indonesia, the Corruption Eradication Commission (*Komisi Pemberantasan Korupsi*—KPK) was established as an independent institution responsible for preventing, investigating, and prosecuting corruption offenses. According to the KPK, the principal forms of corruption include acts causing losses to state finances, bribery, embezzlement in office, extortion, fraudulent practices, conflicts of interest in public procurement, and the acceptance of unlawful gratuities. The factors contributing to corruption may originate from either internal or external sources related to the perpetrator. Internal factors arise from the individual's mindset, character, and behavior. These include excessive greed and an insatiable desire for wealth or power, weak moral integrity that enables individuals to engage in corrupt practices, and a consumptive lifestyle among public officials that encourages illicit financial gain. In some cases, family expectations and pressures may also contribute to corrupt behavior.

External factors, on the other hand, are conditions outside the individual that facilitate or encourage corruption. These include societal attitudes that tolerate or normalize corrupt practices, economic pressures, political influences, and organizational weaknesses. Organizational factors may involve a lack of exemplary leadership, where senior officials fail to demonstrate integrity and ethical conduct that can serve as a model for subordinates. Likewise, the absence of a strong organizational culture founded on ethical values creates an environment conducive to misconduct. Inadequate accountability mechanisms and weak internal and external oversight further increase opportunities for corruption, collusion, and nepotism within public institutions.

Efforts to eradicate corruption, collusion, and nepotism (KKN) in Indonesia have been undertaken for a long time. Substantial efforts and resources have been allocated to addressing these issues, as their presence causes significant harm not only to the economy but also to the political, social, and bureaucratic systems of the country. However, these anti-corruption efforts have not yet had a substantial impact on the persistently high number of corruption cases in Indonesia.

The Indonesian Corruption Watch (ICW) reported in its study on corruption cases in state-owned enterprises (SOEs) that law enforcement agencies investigated 119 cases involving 340 suspects during the period 2016–2021.² This number continues to increase over time. In addition, data from the Anti-Corruption Clearing House (ACCH) indicates that between 2004 and 2018, corruption cases handled in Indonesia included 1,135 investigations, 887 inquiries, 719 prosecutions, 578 cases with final and binding decisions (*inkracht*), and 610 executed sentences. These figures demonstrate that despite sustained anti-corruption initiatives, corruption remains a persistent and systemic problem in Indonesia.

Corruption poses significant harm to various stakeholders; therefore, the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) continues to develop and implement strategies aimed at eradicating corruption comprehensively, with the ultimate goal of eliminating it from Indonesia. Efforts to combat corruption, collusion, and nepotism must be undertaken collaboratively by multiple actors, not solely by government officials. A cross-sectoral collaboration involving all elements of society is essential to ensure the effectiveness of anti-corruption initiatives.

In many corruption cases, perpetrators are public officials who abuse their authority. Although many of these officials possess strong educational backgrounds, higher education does not necessarily guarantee personal integrity. This condition reflects a fundamental weakness in the education system, which has not been fully successful in producing individuals with strong moral responsibility, as evidenced by the persistence of unethical practices such as corruption, collusion, and nepotism. Ideally, the Indonesian education system should be capable of producing a generation of highly competent and responsible individuals who are prepared to assume significant roles in governance and public administration in the future.

The weakness of Indonesia's education system in cultivating moral reasoning and ethical intelligence in

² Egiyoga, "Jumlah Kasus Korupsi yang Disidik," *Antikorupsi.org*, 2022, <https://antikorupsi.org/taxonomy/term/503#:~:text=Jumlah%20kasus%20korupsi%20yang%20disidik,dan%209%20kasus%20pada%202021>

decision-making has contributed to the failure to fully realize the constitutional mandate contained in the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution, particularly the objective of educating the life of the nation (*mencerdaskan kehidupan bangsa*). The Indonesian government adopts two main approaches in its efforts to prevent corruption.³ The first is to position students as the primary target of anti-corruption education. The second is to empower students to influence their surrounding environment so that it becomes less permissive toward corrupt practices. This approach implies that an anti-corruption mentality must be instilled from an early stage, particularly among school students, given the importance of nurturing such values so that they remain embedded as they grow into future generations who will bear significant responsibility in governing the state.

Therefore, the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) has ultimately advocated for the inclusion of anti-corruption education at all levels of education in Indonesia, particularly at the tertiary level. The integration of anti-corruption education serves as a preventive policy output aimed at reducing the occurrence of corruption, collusion, and nepotism (KKN). At the university level, this program is intended to introduce and educate students across Indonesia about corruption and its eradication, while simultaneously instilling anti-corruption values so that students develop a strong ethical orientation and are encouraged to actively participate in anti-corruption efforts as part of their civic responsibility.

The values that must be cultivated to develop an anti-corruption mentality include honesty, care, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, courage, and fairness. In addition, students engaged in anti-corruption education are expected to uphold key principles such as accountability, transparency, fairness, policy prudence, and policy control. The internalization of these values and principles is expected to produce a generation with strong anti-corruption integrity, which in the long term will not only reduce the number of corruption cases but may also eliminate corrupt

³ Yusrianto Kadir, "Kebijakan Pendidikan Anti Korupsi di Perguruan Tinggi," *Gorontalo Law Review* 1, no. 1 (2018).

practices, collusion, and nepotism across various sectors of state governance.

In this context, collaboration between the KPK and the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia is essential to incorporate anti-corruption education into the curriculum of all higher education institutions in Indonesia. The implementation of this course may take various instructional forms, including in-class discussions, case studies, improvement system scenarios, general lectures, film-based discussions, investigative reports, thematic exploration, prototype development, policy evaluation exercises, and educational tool-based learning. Through these diverse pedagogical approaches, the program is expected to enhance public participation—particularly among university students—in combating corruption, collusion, and nepotism in Indonesia.

B. Method

This study employs a normative legal research method. The primary legal materials used include the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and other relevant statutory regulations. Secondary legal materials consist of scholarly literature, academic journals, and other library-based sources. The data collection technique is conducted through library research, combined with a statutory approach and a conceptual approach. All data and information obtained in this study are analyzed using a descriptive qualitative method.

C. Result and Discussion

1. The Role of Anti-Corruption Education in Higher Education

In recent years, corruption has become widespread in various countries, including Indonesia. In Indonesia, data obtained from the Anti-Corruption Clearing House (ACCH) indicate that corruption cases handled between 2004 and 2018 comprise 1,135 investigations, 887 inquiries, 719 prosecutions, 578 cases with final and binding decisions (*inkracht*), and 610

executed cases.⁴ The high number of corruption cases in Indonesia demonstrates that the country is in a critical condition and highly vulnerable to corrupt practices.

Corruption is a form of immoral conduct committed by individuals holding positions of authority who abuse their power, resulting in harm to various parties. Corruption can be perpetrated by anyone, ranging from lower-level members of society to middle and upper social strata, including public officials at both local and central government levels.⁵ The prevailing conditions indicate that society is continuously exposed to corrupt practices involving state administrators. This situation is closely related to the low level of integrity among perpetrators and the persistence of a permissive culture toward corruption. In addition, opportunities and personal motives to enrich oneself and one's close associates also contribute significantly to the occurrence of corrupt acts. Corruption in Indonesia appears to have become normalized within social practices; however, it remains a behavior that fundamentally contradicts both moral values and legal norms.⁶

The Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) has stated that corruption is an extraordinary crime. This characterization is based on the increasingly sophisticated methods of corruption, which require equally extraordinary measures to combat and eradicate it. In addition, the widespread occurrence of corruption in Indonesia causes significant losses to the state and the national economy, while also hindering efforts to achieve a just and prosperous society.⁷ According to the KPK, all of these practices constitute acts of corruption that have wide-ranging impacts on various aspects of state and social life.

⁴ Anti-Corruption Clearing House, "Statistik Tindak Pidana Korupsi," *ACCH KPK*, 2018, <https://acch.kpk.go.id/id/statistik/tindak-pidana-korupsi>.

⁵ O. Y. Yanto, S. Samiyono, S. Walangitan, and R. Rachmayanthi, "Mengoptimalkan Peran Perguruan Tinggi dalam Mengurangi Perilaku Korupsi," *Jurnal Legislati Indonesia* 17, no. 1 (2020): 70–84.

⁶ Adwirman, Andi Parellangi, et al., *Buku Ajar Pendidikan dan Budaya Antikorupsi* (Jakarta: Pusat Pendidikan dan Pelatihan Tenaga Kesehatan, 2014).

⁷ H. M. P. Simarmata, S. Sahri, S. Subagio, S. Syafrizal, B. Purba, P. B. Purba, et al., *Pengantar Pendidikan Anti Korupsi* (Yayasan Kita Menulis, 2020).

Since corruption can be committed by any member of society, collective action and cooperation are essential.

Therefore, it is necessary for all citizens to engage in self-reflection and to internalize anti-corruption values in their daily social activities. It is imperative for Indonesia to take immediate and decisive action to halt the occurrence of corruption. If anti-corruption efforts are not effectively implemented, they may lead to serious consequences that harm societal, national, and state life. The persistence of corruption in Indonesia has reached a level that generates widespread skepticism across all segments of society. The prevalence of corruption cases involving highly educated public officials ultimately reflects a weakness in Indonesia's education system in producing generations that are both intellectually capable and morally grounded. Public officials involved in corruption typically come from strong educational backgrounds, indicating that such positions are not occupied without consideration of competence and integrity. Therefore, one of the preventive measures against corruption is the role of higher education in providing anti-corruption education within academic environments.

Higher education serves as a platform for developing future intellectuals with strong character, grounded in the Tri Dharma of Higher Education, namely education and teaching, research and development, and community service. As stipulated in Article 4 of Law No. 12 of 2012 on Higher Education, higher education functions to: (a) develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of the nation in order to enhance national intellectual life; (b) develop an academic community that is innovative, responsive, creative, skilled, competitive, and cooperative through the implementation of the Tri Dharma; and (c) develop science and technology by considering and applying humanistic values.

Therefore, higher education plays a crucial role in national development, particularly in shaping students as future agents of change. Higher education institutions play a central role in the preventive efforts against corruption, particularly in instilling integrity values among students, enhancing legal awareness, and fostering an anti-corruption culture.

Accordingly, higher education has an obligation to implement various preventive measures against corruption, especially by cultivating an anti-corruption culture,⁸ strengthening legal consciousness, and embedding integrity values in students. This responsibility becomes even more significant in light of the enactment of various legal and policy instruments aimed at strengthening anti-corruption efforts within the national education system.

Each higher education institution should be able to provide anti-corruption education in the form of compulsory or elective courses integrated into the higher education curriculum. Anti-corruption education aims to cultivate an anti-corruption character within students and to build their awareness, motivation, and competencies as agents of change in creating a clean society and state free from the threat of corruption.⁹ Accordingly, the teaching of anti-corruption education in higher education institutions may include materials on global corruption phenomena, corruption issues in Indonesia, and various approaches to combating corruption, including legal, business, market-based, and cultural perspectives.

It also emphasizes the important role of the younger generation in combating corruption as agents of change, among other relevant themes. The inculcation of anti-corruption values among students can be carried out through formal education, socialization programs, seminars, campaigns, and other extracurricular activities. In this sense, anti-corruption education for university students is directed toward value-based education, particularly the internalization of moral and ethical values.¹⁰

The implementation of anti-corruption education in higher education institutions, students as future leaders of the

⁸ P. P. Saifulloh, "Peran Perguruan Tinggi dalam Menumbuhkan Budaya Anti Korupsi di Indonesia," *Jurnal Hukum & Pembangunan* 47, no. 4 (2017): 459-476.

⁹ Tim Penulis Buku Pendidikan Anti Korupsi, *Pendidikan Anti Korupsi untuk Perguruan Tinggi* (Jakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 2011).

¹⁰ Y. Kadir, "Kebijakan Pendidikan Anti Korupsi di Perguruan Tinggi," *Gorontalo Law Review* 1, no. 1 (2018): 25-38.

nation are expected to become individuals who are free from and immune to practices of corruption, collusion, and nepotism (KKN). This is particularly important considering that students are individuals pursuing higher education and are therefore expected to serve as role models for others while remaining accountable for their actions. Moreover, students are assigned several key roles and functions, namely as agents of change, social control, iron stock, and moral force. As agents of change, students are expected to be sensitive to various social issues occurring in society and to actively seek solutions to these problems. They are also required to utilize their intellectual capacity to contribute to national development and to serve as a bridge between society and the government in conveying aspirations and promoting constructive change.

As social control, students are expected to be capable of social interaction and to critically observe social conditions within their environment. They also play a role in providing suggestions, criticism, and solutions to societal problems, while demonstrating sensitivity, concern, and tangible contributions to current social issues. Furthermore, as iron stock, students are viewed as the nation's future human resources who must possess strong character and adequate competencies to replace previous generations. They are expected to demonstrate independence, responsibility, and mastery of science and technology (STEM) in facing future challenges, thereby becoming valuable assets for the nation. As a moral force, students are responsible for upholding moral values in daily life, serving as ethical role models, and actively engaging with society in a responsible and meaningful manner.

2. Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education in Higher Education Institutions

Anti-corruption education is an essential instrument for fostering changes in anti-corruption attitudes among the current generation in order to safeguard the integrity of the nation and the state. Efforts to combat corruption are not sufficient if limited only to the arrest and punishment of corrupt offenders. Such efforts must also be accompanied by preventive measures through education and character building for the

younger generation. Anti-corruption values are therefore crucial to be instilled in today's youth. These values are expected to transform corrupt systems and cultures among the younger generation. Young people are generally characterized by a strong desire for freedom and a process of identity formation. In order to guide this developmental stage away from corrupt tendencies, the internalization of anti-corruption values becomes necessary.

The anti-corruption values that need to be cultivated among the younger generation are as follows:

- A. **Honesty**, according to the *Indonesian Dictionary (Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia)*, is derived from the word "jujur",¹¹ which means sincerity and integrity of heart. According to Mustari, honesty is an action or behavior aimed at becoming a person who can always be trusted in every action. The value of honesty is one of the fundamental traits that must be possessed by the younger generation, not only in relation to corruption but in all aspects of life. Honesty fosters an authentic personality and enables individuals to remain true to themselves. This value can be developed from the closest environment, particularly the family and educational settings, as part of efforts to build an honest younger generation.
- B. **Responsibility** can be defined as a condition in which an individual is obliged to bear or fulfill the consequences arising from their own actions or those of others.¹² In this sense, it means that every person must perform certain duties or obligations as a form of accountability for the consequences they face. The younger generation must possess a sense of responsibility toward the duties entrusted to them, thereby fostering a personality that is obedient to rules and regulations.

¹¹ *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI)*, "Jujur," <https://kbbi.web.id/jujur>

¹² Pusat Bahasa, *Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia* (Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional, 2002), 1139.

- C. **Courage**, derived from the word "*brave*", refers to firmness of heart, strong self-confidence, and similar qualities. In the educational environment, courage among the younger generation can be developed by fostering the willingness to take responsibility and to be honest. Through these values, the younger generation is expected to develop the courage to fight and eradicate corruption cases that occur in society.
- D. **Justice** comes from the word "*just*", which means equal, balanced, impartial, or not taking sides. A sense of justice among the younger generation, especially university students, can serve as a foundation for building an anti-corruption generation. In practice, students can apply justice by not discriminating in friendships and by avoiding behaviors that demean others.
- E. **Discipline** is derived from the word "*disciplined*", which refers to orderliness, obedience, or compliance with rules. Discipline begins with self-regulation, by establishing personal rules and consistently adhering to them. Discipline encourages individuals to obey regulations and to be reluctant to violate them. In the context of students, discipline can be demonstrated through serious study habits and timely completion of assignments.

Corruption ultimately reflects a lack of legal awareness and legal compliance among perpetrators, as it constitutes a criminal act prohibited by law. By engaging in corruption, an individual simultaneously betrays the Indonesian Constitution and prioritizes personal gain through the abuse of power. However, the high number of corruption cases among public officials indicates that higher education does not necessarily guarantee strong morality and integrity in carrying out entrusted responsibilities and official duties. Anti-corruption education has therefore become an important learning component for university students as a preventive effort to reduce the prevalence of corruption among young people, both now and in the future. It is implemented as an effort to develop high-quality human resources with integrity and free from corruption. In higher education institutions, students are

introduced to fundamental knowledge related to anti-corruption education and are expected to understand its concepts as well as preventive measures.

In Indonesia, the curriculum places Anti-Corruption Education as a compulsory general course as part of higher education efforts to instill anti-corruption awareness among students. In the implementation of learning and the delivery of anti-corruption education materials, several instructional designs are required as follows:

A. Knowledge of Corruption

Students must be able to understand the concept of corruption itself, including what constitutes corrupt behavior and what attitudes should be taken in response to it. Lecturers play a guiding role in directing students toward a correct and comprehensive understanding of corruption. Students may obtain information regarding corrupt practices and various forms of corruption from different media sources, enabling them to analyze corruption in relation to other types of criminal behavior. Therefore, it is necessary to provide explanations regarding the causes of corruption by linking them to relevant theories, types of corruption, and the consequences that arise from such acts.

With the various corruption cases that have occurred, students are expected to develop their own analyses and arguments regarding acts of corruption. Students can examine corruption cases from multiple perspectives of life, including moral aspects, which can provide broader insight. These elements serve as a fundamental basis for fostering anti-corruption awareness among students in developing high-quality human resources. Based on students' knowledge and understanding of the concept of corruption, it is expected that efforts can be made to instill and shape anti-corruption attitudes and character.¹³

¹³ Ahmad Fikri Hardin and Reja Fahlevi, "Desain Bahan Ajar Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan Berbasis Pendidikan Anti Korupsi di Perguruan Tinggi," *Jurnal Moral Kemasyarakatan* 2 (2016): 168.

B. Development of Anti-Corruption Attitudes

The instillation and formation of anti-corruption attitudes and character must be accompanied by moral education. According to Chaplin, morality refers to attitudes, behavior, or ethics that conform to applicable social norms in society, including laws, customs, and prevailing traditions. Morality serves as an essential foundation for students in developing strong attitudes and character. This development focuses on shaping students into individuals who possess anti-corruption values and integrity. Students must be able to evaluate objects, in this case corrupt practices, based on their knowledge and understanding of corruption. They are also expected to have strong cognitive abilities in processing and understanding information related to corruption. In addition, the development of anti-corruption attitudes can be carried out through various activities that incorporate anti-corruption values.

C. Development of Creativity and Skills

In its implementation, anti-corruption education is grounded in values that exist within society and are formalized into various regulations, both legal and social. Within social regulations, morality and convention offer different perspectives in assessing human actions. A conventional perspective considers an action acceptable as long as it is not explicitly prohibited, whereas morality evaluates actions based on prevailing norms and ethical principles. Conventional norms tend to have a narrower scope, as they may apply only within one or several groups. Therefore, anti-corruption education should incorporate both moral and conventional perspectives. In this regard, anti-corruption education is based on the moral maturity development of students. However, it is important to emphasize that corruption is universally considered wrong, both from moral and conventional perspectives.

Furthermore, the implementation of anti-corruption education is fully entrusted to higher education institutions and lecturers in determining the appropriate learning methods for students. Naturally, the delivery of course materials is expected to be easily understood by students through effective and accessible teaching approaches. There are various learning

models that can be applied in the implementation of student learning, which are adopted by lecturers in different universities across Indonesia. According to the Directorate General of Higher Education (DIKTI), Ministry of National Education (Depdiknas), several teaching methods can be implemented, namely:

A. Discussion

In this method, students are encouraged to engage in classroom discussions on the assigned topics. The lecturer acts as a facilitator, while students are expected to actively contribute analyses and arguments related to the discussion topics. This learning approach aims to develop students' awareness, sensitivity, and critical thinking skills in formulating problems. Students are also encouraged to draw their own conclusions based on the discussion outcomes.

B. Case Study

The case study method involves examining corruption cases based on previously provided conceptual materials delivered by the lecturer. This method aims to enhance students' ability to analyze cases using corruption concepts and to increase their sensitivity toward corruption issues occurring in society. Case studies may focus on major corruption cases, societal corruption problems, or government handling of corruption cases.

C. System Development Scenario

This method is similar to case studies; however, students are required to design improvement scenarios and problem-solving systems based on the analyzed cases. The objective is to stimulate students' ability to identify practical solutions and to strengthen their analytical skills in addressing corruption-related problems.

D. Film Discussion

As the name suggests, this method uses films as a learning medium. Students are shown films related to corruption cases, which are then analyzed. From the screening, students are expected to conduct analysis by connecting the content to previously learned materials, including types of corruption, causes, and solutions. This

method aims to improve students' comprehension and analytical capacity.

E. Policy Analysis and Implementation Evaluation

Based on corruption cases handled by the government, students analyze policies or measures taken in addressing such cases. This analysis may be conducted through legal reasoning or legal opinion writing. Students may also observe the implementation of government policies in practice, comparing official commitments with real-world outcomes as a reflection of integrity.

F. Integrated Writing Skills Development

Through this method, students are expected to analyze, summarize, and develop issues into structured academic writing using proper grammar and writing conventions. The purpose is to enhance students' ability to present facts and ideas in an integrated manner based on corruption-related learning materials.

All of these learning methods are implemented within the Anti-Corruption Education course, which carries a weight of 2 credits. The role of higher education institutions is crucial in achieving the objectives of this course, as they serve as the main channel for delivering anti-corruption knowledge. Each university is expected to optimize these learning methods for all students so that they develop an anti-corruption mindset.¹⁴ Anti-corruption education has significant urgency in preventing and eradicating corruption cases. Therefore, it is essential to instill anti-corruption education in the younger generation, especially university students, in order to build a corruption-free generation and high-quality human resources. This will also have an impact on Indonesia's future, particularly in facing the demographic bonus. Anti-corruption education plays an important role in realizing a corruption-free Indonesia by fostering critical thinking, accuracy, and problem-solving abilities among students in addressing corruption issues.

¹⁴ Asian Development Bank, *Anticorruption Policy* (Manila: ADB, 1998).

3. The Impact of Anti-Corruption Education on Students as the Younger Generation

Corruption, according to the Asian Development Bank, refers to improper and unlawful behavior in the public and/or private sectors intended to enrich oneself or one's close associates. The factors contributing to corruption are generally divided into internal and external factors. One of the internal factors is the loss of anti-corruption values within individuals, such as honesty, care, independence, discipline, responsibility, hard work, and courage.

This is consistent with the theory proposed by Jack Bologne,¹⁵ also known as the GONE Theory, which explains corruption through four main factors:

- A. **Greeds**, or greed, refers to an excessive desire for more without regard for the means used to achieve it.
- B. **Opportunities** refer to conditions or situations created by institutions or society that allow corruption to occur due to weak awareness or enforcement of anti-corruption values.
- C. **Needs** refer to increasing personal needs influenced by lifestyle development.
- D. **Exposure** refers to the environmental response or consequences faced by perpetrators when their fraudulent actions are discovered.

These factors are highly dependent on an individual's morality. If society possesses strong moral values and a high sense of responsibility, corruption can be minimized, as individuals with strong ethical character are less likely to engage in immoral acts such as corruption. In addition, according to Albert and Chard,¹⁶ corruption and fraudulent

¹⁵ Jack Bologne, *Reframing Corruption: GONE Theory in Organizational Ethics* (New York: Academic Press, 2006).

¹⁶ Donald R. Cressey, *Other People's Money: A Study in the Social Psychology of Embezzlement* (Glencoe, IL: Free Press, 1953); and W. Steve Albrecht et al., *Fraud Examination* (Boston: Cengage Learning, various editions), which

behavior can be explained through three main pillars commonly referred to as the *Fraud Triangle*. These three components consist of pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. Pressure refers to financial or psychological incentives that push an individual toward committing fraud. Opportunity relates to weaknesses in internal control systems or organizational structures that allow fraud to occur. Meanwhile, rationalization refers to the cognitive justification used by perpetrators to legitimize their unethical behavior. These three elements must coexist for fraudulent behavior, including corruption, to take place.

Figure 1.
Fraud Triangle Theory

According to these factors, corruption can be understood as resulting from the deterioration of an individual's character. Efforts to combat corruption have actually been carried out repeatedly; however, such efforts will not be optimal if only the government is involved without the participation of society. Therefore, students who are considered an essential part of society and regarded as agents of change are expected to actively participate in corruption prevention efforts. Students' active role in combating corruption can begin with preventive actions.

further develops the fraud triangle framework often attributed in later literature to Albrecht and other fraud theorists.

To play this role effectively, students must be equipped with strong knowledge and character and must internalize anti-corruption values. One of the efforts to ensure students understand these values is through anti-corruption education. Anti-corruption education is based on three domains. First, the cognitive domain, where students are expected to recognize types of corruption and fundamental concepts of anti-corruption education. Second, the affective domain, where students are able to apply their knowledge in everyday behavior and attitudes. Third, the psychomotor domain, which involves the development of practical skills used to promote and campaign anti-corruption movements.

The regulation governing anti-corruption education is stipulated in the Minister of Research, Technology, and Higher Education Regulation (Permenristekdikti) No. 33 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education (PAK) in Higher Education Institutions. Anti-corruption education is mandatory to be implemented through a dedicated course. Article 1 of Permenristekdikti No. 33 of 2019 states that anti-corruption education is a learning process and behavioral formation conducted in higher education institutions related to the prevention of corrupt behavior and criminal acts of corruption. The implementation of the Anti-Corruption Education course has been increasingly integrated into the curriculum of higher education institutions in Indonesia. The prevention of corrupt behavior can be achieved when students understand anti-corruption values and internalize them in their character and daily life.

In addition to anti-corruption values, there are also anti-corruption principles that must be understood and applied in daily life, including:

- A. **Accountability**, which refers to the alignment between applicable rules and the implementation of work, where the resulting outputs must be accountable. For example, students are expected to comply with applicable regulations when carrying out academic or organizational activities.
- B. **Transparency** is a key principle in anti-corruption efforts, as it requires that all policy processes be

conducted openly so that the public can be aware of any irregularities. Among students, transparency can be applied by ensuring that reports of student activities are accessible to all students.

- C. **Fairness** serves to ensure that actions and decisions are not excessive or unreasonable. In practice, this can be applied by avoiding exaggeration in activity reports or academic documentation.
- D. **Policy** functions as a regulatory framework that ensures actions do not harm the state, society, or fellow students.
- E. **Policy control** refers to efforts to ensure that established policies are effectively implemented. In the student context, this principle can be applied through continuous monitoring and evaluation of student-related activities, from program planning and implementation to reporting stages.

The main objective of anti-corruption education for students is to enable them to understand anti-corruption values, these principles, the underlying causes of corruption, and methods of prevention, so that they can better recognize the characteristics of corrupt behavior. Furthermore, with the knowledge acquired, students as agents of change are expected to develop strong character, instill an anti-corruption culture, and actively participate in corruption prevention efforts. In the long term, anti-corruption education is expected to produce graduates who are professional, have integrity, are committed, and uphold anti-corruption principles. In the present context, the immediate impact is the increasing awareness and knowledge of anti-corruption values among students.

D. Conclusion

Corruption is recognized as an extraordinary crime, and the persistently high number of corruption cases in Indonesia underscores the need for comprehensive preventive measures alongside law enforcement. Corruption encompasses various unlawful acts, including state financial losses, bribery, embezzlement, extortion, fraudulent practices, conflicts of interest in public procurement, and illegal gratuities. The causes of corruption stem from both internal and external factors. The

GONE Theory identifies Greed, Opportunity, Need, and Exposure as the primary drivers of corrupt behavior, while the Fraud Triangle Theory explains that corruption is encouraged by the interaction of Pressure, Opportunity, and Rationalization. Recognizing these underlying causes, the Indonesian Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), in collaboration with the Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education, introduced Anti-Corruption Education as a preventive strategy. This initiative was institutionalized through the Minister of Research, Technology, and Higher Education Regulation No. 33 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of Anti-Corruption Education in Higher Education Institutions, which requires universities to offer Anti-Corruption Education as a compulsory course.

The primary objective of Anti-Corruption Education is to cultivate integrity and strengthen students' legal awareness by instilling core anti-corruption values, including honesty, discipline, care, responsibility, hard work, simplicity, independence, courage, and justice, as well as the principles of accountability and transparency. As institutions responsible for developing future leaders, universities play a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge, attitudes, and practical skills necessary to prevent corruption through student-centered learning approaches such as classroom discussions, case studies, policy analysis, investigative reports, and community engagement. Beyond increasing students' understanding of corruption and its prevention, Anti-Corruption Education is expected to shape graduates who possess strong moral character, professionalism, and a high sense of social responsibility. By reinforcing students' roles as agents of change, social controllers, iron stock, and moral forces, this educational initiative contributes to the long-term goal of fostering a generation committed to integrity and supporting the realization of a corruption-free Indonesia.

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